

Towards low carbon transport infrastructure in the Nordics

Comparative study on embodied carbon
management for road and rail infrastructure
across the Nordic countries

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Abbreviations

BIM	Building Information Modelling
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CO ₂ e	Carbon Dioxide equivalent
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DRD	Danish Road Directorate (Vejdirektoratet)
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
FTIA	Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency (Väylävirasto)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPP	Green Public Procurement
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IRCA	Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration (Vegagerðin)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NPRA	Norwegian Public Roads Administration (Statens vegvesen)
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
STA	Swedish Transport Administration (Trafikverket)

Glossary

Embodied carbon	Emissions related to the production, construction, maintenance, and eventual demolition of the materials used throughout a building's life cycle.
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	A systematic process for evaluating the potential environmental consequences of a proposed project or policy, aiming to inform decision-makers and mitigate adverse effects before implementation.
Environmental product declaration (EPD)	An environmental product declaration provides quantified environmental data on the life cycle of products (and services), enabling comparison between products that fulfil the same function.
Green Public Procurement (GPP)	Approach in which public actors purchase goods, services and works with reduced environmental impacts, encouraging sustainable production and consumption practices across sectors.
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	A measure of a greenhouse gas's ability to trap heat in the atmosphere over a specific timeframe, expressed relative to carbon dioxide, to assess its impact on global warming.
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a tool used to quantify the environmental impacts of a system across its entire life cycle, encompassing all production and consumption processes.
Operational carbon	Emissions generated from the energy required to operate buildings, such as heating, cooling, and lighting.

Executive Summary

Transport infrastructure is a major source of greenhouse gas emissions, mainly stemming from material production, transport, construction, and maintenance. Historically, efforts to reduce the climate impact of the transport sector have focused primarily on operational emissions – those generated by vehicles during use. While these measures are essential, they do not address the full climate impact of transport infrastructure.

Embodied carbon – deriving from material production, construction, maintenance and reinvestment of infrastructure assets – contributes significantly to the carbon footprint of road and rail infrastructure projects but has received far less attention in transport-related policy developments. Estimates for Sweden, for instance, have found that the infrastructure sector's embodied carbon accounted for roughly 10% of road and rail transport emissions in 2022.¹ Reducing these emissions, through the increased uptake of low-carbon materials and construction processes, is essential for achieving established emission reduction targets and goals of climate neutrality.

Integrating emissions reduction goals throughout the full infrastructure project cycle, addressing all stages, activities and actors, is a complex task. As a consequence, although many pathways to reducing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure exist – such as selecting low-carbon materials, optimising designs to use less material, and enhancing recycling and reuse – current efforts are often not enough to significantly reduce emissions.

A comparative review of how road and rail infrastructure projects are managed in the Nordics highlights similar processes for planning transport infrastructure across countries, with rail and road infrastructure bodies playing prominent roles in managing embodied carbon across the Nordic countries. Specifically, these infrastructure bodies generally set carbon targets and evaluate emissions for infrastructure projects, often while working alongside external contractors. This collaboration is vital for ensuring consistent and measurable reductions in embodied carbon at project level. When it comes to Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) and public procurement, a broader range of stakeholders is typically engaged.

However, this study uncovers complex decision-making processes, diverse carbon management practices, and diffuse responsibilities for the reduction of embodied carbon (see Figure O-1). The study identifies four areas of infrastructure project management that are relevant for the reduction of embodied carbon: infrastructure planning, carbon management, EIA and public procurement, which all constitute opportunities to trigger a reduction of embodied carbon in infrastructure. The study also identifies four types of actors who can play a role in the reduction of embodied carbon: ministries, supervising entities, infrastructure bodies and external partners (such as contractors).

The study showcases good practices for reducing embodied carbon in infrastructure projects in the Nordic countries. With important progress on embodied carbon already being made across the region and a strong collaborative approach to assessing the climate impacts of transport infrastructure, the Nordic countries serve as an inspiring example from which valuable lessons and insights can be drawn.

Numerous initiatives, tools and methodologies currently exist and are being implemented in the Nordic countries to facilitate the adoption of low-carbon solutions in transport infrastructure projects. National infrastructure authorities hold significant influence and can leverage their purchasing power to boost demand for low-carbon materials and activities. By doing so, they encourage industries to invest in decarbonisation, increase the supply of low-carbon options, and foster competition on material carbon footprints, potentially lowering green premiums.

However, there is no silver bullet for successfully addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure. Instead, a multifaceted approach is needed to effectively reduce emissions from materials and construction-related activities, involving all relevant decision-makers and combining a variety of tools and instruments.

The review also suggests an increased, continued commitment among the Nordic countries to tackle climate impacts associated with infrastructure development. Several opportunities exist for developing more comprehensive approaches to managing and reducing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure:

¹ Ramboll estimate based data from STA's 2023 annual report (STA (2024a). 'Trafikverkets årsredovisning 2023') covering GHG emissions from road and rail transport and GHG emissions from construction, operation and maintenance of transport infrastructure.

- **Strengthen the link between strategies at national and infrastructure body-level.** In the Nordics, embodied carbon strategies and targets are developed by the infrastructure bodies themselves, as there are generally no equivalent provisions at government level. However, ambitious governmental strategies that clearly link to those of the infrastructure bodies can play a pivotal role in supporting embodied carbon reduction efforts across the Nordic transport infrastructure sector.
- **Further improve carbon assessment practices.** Carbon calculations and life cycle assessments (LCA) have emerged as common practice across the region, with the Nordics successfully developing LCA tools and implementing the assessment into project planning. Still, as seen in this study, more can be done in terms of improving LCA methodologies and ensuring that the assessments inform decision-making in a systematic manner.
- **Enhance embodied carbon integration in EIAs and their approval procedures.** To further integrate embodied carbon in EIAs, the consistency of embodied carbon assessment should be improved by standardising this in the EIA process. Embodied carbon can then become a determining factor in approval procedures of EIAs. Across the Nordic countries, attempts are made to integrate embodied carbon into the EIAs of infrastructure projects. However, as of now, the characteristics of EIAs as a tool inherently constrain their effectiveness in managing embodied carbon through such climate impact assessments.
- **Leverage material-specific requirements in procurement.** Material-specific requirements can be leveraged to drive demand for low-carbon alternatives with similar performance and safety levels. While the use of procurement requirements to reduce embodied carbon in Nordic infrastructure projects has increased, their potential to drive demand for low-carbon materials and solutions remains underutilised. Challenges in implementation, such as establishing baselines and effectively measuring and monitoring carbon performance throughout a project's life cycle, limit the effectiveness of broad project-level reduction targets.

Ultimately, the study concludes that full integration of embodied carbon considerations into the infrastructure decision-making framework across the Nordic countries is still a work in progress. Going forward, efforts need to be scaled up, transitioning from low-carbon pilot projects to strategy-driven action.

The Nordics can serve as inspiration for other European countries and beyond. Good practices for reducing embodied carbon of infrastructure projects, numerous initiatives, tools and methodologies are currently being used or are under development, which indicates a frontrunner position for the Nordic countries.

Four action areas through which to address embodied carbon in transport infrastructure are identified: embodied carbon targets and framework, carbon assessment, tools and data management, EIA, GPP (see Table O-1). The action areas outlined provide a solid foundation for addressing the embodied carbon of transport infrastructure while recognising varying levels of maturity and ambition. Specific actions identified within these areas constitute a practical guide for addressing embodied carbon, adaptable to each country's context and governance structure.

Based on these action areas, a set of recommendations is provided, indicating prerequisites for reducing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure across the EU.

The recommendations focus on the necessity to set embodied carbon targets, integrate mandatory carbon assessment frameworks, and develop open-access databases for monitoring.

Figure 0-1. Overview of main aspects and actors involved in addressing embodied carbon in Nordic infrastructure

		Denmark				Finland				Iceland				Norway				Sweden			
		Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors
Planning	Identification of need																				
	Feasibility studies																				
	Final project approval	*								*											
	Design																				
	Construction																				
Carbon management	Targets on embodied carbon in infrastructure																				
	Monitoring embodied carbon performance																				
	Ownership of carbon assessment tool																				
	Conducting carbon assessment																				
	Carbon shadow pricing																				
EIA	Commissioning EIA																				
	Conducting EIA																				
	Approving EIA																				
Public procurement	Providing policy on GPP																				
	Requiring GWP documentation																				
	Verifying of EPDs																				
	Benchmarks values																				

Legend

- Main actor involved
- Supporting actor
- No current implementation

*Final approval provided by parliament

Note: This is a simplified overview; variations will occur depending on project size and type as well as procurement model. The role of procurement authorities is not highlighted in this overview.

Table 0-1. Key action areas for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure

		Level 0 (low ambition)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (highest ambition)
Embodied carbon targets, databases and framework	Specific embodied carbon targets on transport infrastructure	Embodied carbon is not acknowledged as part of the strategy.	Embodied carbon is acknowledged as part of the strategy, but no specific targets are set.	Partial targets for embodied carbon (i.e. for certain life cycle modules), initial focus on reducing GWP for high-carbon materials.	Complete targets for embodied carbon, includes specific, long-term GWP limits for carbon-intensive materials.
	Framework on embodied carbon assessment	No framework to support embodied carbon assessments.	Embodied carbon assessments are voluntary.	Embodied carbon assessments are conditionally mandatory (e.g. based on project size or type).	Embodied carbon assessments are always mandatory.
	Embodied carbon performance monitoring	No monitoring of embodied carbon.	Basic monitoring with no connection to targets.	Monitoring with defined targets, but not necessarily used for decision-making.	Comprehensive monitoring against targets with effective management reporting, supporting data-driven decision-making.
	Database (monitoring carbon performance)	No database.	Carbon assessment is documented with one value only, but detailed carbon assessment is not collected and stored.	Detailed carbon assessment is collected and stored, but the database is closed.	Open national database for detailed carbon assessments, with product-level data to enable benchmarking of materials by quantities, GWP values and costs.
Carbon assessment, tools and data management	Embodied carbon assessment methods	No specified standards or guidelines which should be used.	Basic guidelines established.	Standards and common assessment methods are followed through a specific tool.	Standards and assessment methods are aligned and can be implemented independently of any specific tool.

Table 0-1. Key action areas for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure (continued)

		Level 0 (low ambition)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (highest ambition)
Carbon assessment, tools and data management	Tools for carbon assessments	No specific tools.	Basic tools in use, e.g. Excel.	Advanced tools standardised across projects.	Sophisticated and dynamic BIM-connected tools.
	Database (emission factors)	Global/generic database, minimal product-level specificity.	National, tool-based database including some product-level details.	Extensive, open-access national database with substantial product-specific data.	Verified national database for accounting with product-specific data and possibility for integration across tools (e.g. API interfaces).
EIA	Embodied carbon considerations in EIAs	No embodied carbon consideration in EIAs.	Embodied carbon assessment conducted as part of EIA on a voluntary basis.	Embodied carbon assessment required as part of in EIAs.	Embodied carbon impact is a determinative factor in EIA approval.
GPP	Embodied carbon considerations in procurement policy	Embodied carbon is not considered in procurement.	Embodied carbon is considered voluntarily in procurement, with initial incentives to encourage low-carbon solutions.	Embodied carbon considerations are conditionally mandatory (e.g. based on project size or type), with ambitious requirements.	Embodied carbon considerations are always mandatory, with robust, specific carbon targets integrated across all policies.
	Result in embodied carbon reduction through procurement	Embodied carbon reduction through procurement does not occur.	Procurement practices that contribute to embodied carbon reductions are applied, but on an inconsistent basis.	Procurement that contributes to embodied carbon reduction is consistently applied, with specific thresholds on carbon-intensive materials.	Systematic procurement practices that strongly enhance embodied carbon reduction and applied in all projects.

Foresight Narrative

In the future, we have long-term, consistent, and transparent strategies and regulatory frameworks within the EU, but also globally, that bring predictability to green investments and allow stakeholders to build climate and environmental expertise with strong foresight.

Imagine being in the early phases of an infrastructure construction project. From the very beginning, all members of the value chain have clear and well-defined CO₂e reduction targets integrated into the project plan. These targets are seamlessly embedded into every step of the process, ensuring that everyone knows what they are aiming for and how to achieve it.

When a project idea is born, the project owner has a focus on limiting the full life cycle footprint of the construction work. When the designers open their design tool, they can immediately compare the CO₂e emissions of different alternatives. The option with the lowest impact is selected for the next project phase. When awarding the project team for the planning phase of the project, it is simple to choose the solution that best combines low climate impact and other environmental and social aspects. This is because all the calculations are made within the same design tool; emissions reduction against the early phase alternatives can be made directly in a consistent and traceable manner.

As the project progresses to the construction phase, this same integrated tool continues to guide decision-making. Contractors receive clear guidelines and targets for CO₂e emissions, and they can access real-time data to adjust their methods and materials to stay within the prescribed limits. Each step of the infrastructure asset life cycle - from materials procurement to on-site practices to maintenance - is monitored

and optimised to minimise the embodied carbon footprint. If a particular method or material begins to exceed its projected emissions, the tool offers alternative solutions and adjustments to bring the project back on track. The procurement managers of infrastructure bodies will request the scenarios for reducing the embodied carbon by obtaining shadow prices on construction projects using the most innovative, low-carbon, and standard-compliant materials available on the market.

In this phase, detailed reports are generated automatically, providing insights on emissions at every stage. The reports are easily accessible to relevant stakeholders, ensuring transparency and accountability. In addition, specific data on materials and processes is openly available for value chain actors to benchmark.

The construction team collaborates closely with environmental and technical specialists to implement best practices for reducing embodied carbon. Through continuous monitoring and adjustment, the project not only meets but often exceeds its initial CO₂e reduction targets. This approach, by leveraging advanced planning tools and real-time data, ensures that climate considerations are embedded in every aspect of the construction process, laying a strong foundation for greener and more environmentally responsible infrastructure projects.

Insights gained from completed projects are systematically analysed and documented, feeding into a growing knowledge base. This data is then utilised to refine tools and processes for future projects, ensuring continuous improvement. The lessons learned help to set more accurate targets, identify best practices, and innovate new solutions, creating a cycle of improvement that enhances the sustainability and efficiency of all subsequent projects.

1. Introduction

1.1 The significance of embodied carbon in Nordic transport infrastructure

Transport infrastructure plays a critical role in the functioning of modern societies. Roads, railways, and other transport networks are essential for economic activity, access to services and regional development. As urbanisation increases and movement patterns evolve, the demand for reliable and efficient transport infrastructure continues to rise.

Meanwhile, transport infrastructure is a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, largely due to the embodied emissions associated with the production and transportation of materials, as well as the construction and maintenance activities involved. In Sweden, for instance, the infrastructure sector's embodied carbon accounted for roughly 10% of road and rail transport emissions in 2022.² This highlights the significant impact of these emissions on overall transport emissions and underscores the urgency of addressing them – particularly the emissions linked to construction materials – if the sector is to play its part in meeting national emissions reduction goals and the EU climate neutrality target.

Historically, climate-related transport policies have focused primarily on reducing emissions from transport activities, with comparatively less attention given to the climate impacts of constructing and maintaining transport infrastructure. While progress has been made in the Nordic region to accurately calculate embodied carbon from road and rail infrastructure investments, gaps persist in relation to the effective management of these emissions sources in line with established climate targets. Moreover, limitations in reliable monitoring make it challenging to differentiate emissions

sources consistently, within and between infrastructure projects. Unlike the building sector, for which the EU has adopted the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD),³ mandating the assessment and standardisation of embodied carbon calculations for new buildings in accordance with the European standard EN 15978, no equivalent regulations have been implemented at European level for the assessment and management of embodied emissions in infrastructure projects. In the absence of such a framework, regulation is introduced on a country-by-country basis, leading to varied approaches and different ambition levels.

Recent estimations have further highlighted the challenge, indicating a very long carbon payback time (CPBT) for major infrastructure projects, which in certain cases might even exceed the expected lifetime of the infrastructure itself (see the two examples in Table 1-1). This is primarily due to the use of high-carbon materials such as steel, concrete and cement, which are major contributors to the embodied emissions of infrastructure projects. Hence, transitioning to low-carbon materials is a critical step for reducing these emissions.

Despite these challenges, the Nordic countries have made notable progress towards better assessing and addressing embodied carbon in infrastructure projects, often through close dialogue and regional collaboration on the topic. Still, while the Nordics are seen as frontrunners in the area, from which good practices can be identified, more ambitious and systematic action is needed to effectively manage embodied carbon in Nordic infrastructure projects.

² Ramboll estimate based data from STA's 2023 annual report (STA (2024a). 'Trafikverkets årsredovisning 2023') covering GHG emissions from road and rail transport and GHG emissions from construction, operation and maintenance of transport infrastructure.

³ Directive (EU) 2024/1275.

Table 1-1. Expected GHG emission and Carbon Payback Time of selected infrastructure projects

Infrastructure project	Project Description	Expected Project completion	Total Exp. CO2e	Expected project lifetime	Expected Carbon Payback Time
Fehmarn Belt tunnel (Denmark - Germany) ⁴	18 km rail & road tunnel	2029	ca. 2 Mt	120 years	34-181 years
Turku-Helsinki Railroad (Finland) ⁵	193 km railroad	2031	ca. 1 Mt	-	140 years

Box 1.1 Life Cycle Assessments and embodied carbon

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a vital tool for assessing the climate impact of materials, products, and projects. It involves compiling and evaluating the inputs, outputs, and potential environmental effects of products, processes, or services throughout their entire life cycle. An essential part of understanding the carbon footprint of infrastructure projects is distinguishing between embodied and operational carbon throughout the project's life span. According to EN 15643:2021, carbon emissions are categorized as follows:

Operational carbon: Emissions resulting from ongoing activities and the everyday use of infrastructure, such as vehicles on a road or trains on a railway. These impacts fall under life cycle modules B6-B8.

Embodied carbon: Emissions associated with the sourcing, manufacturing, and installation of materials and components used in infrastructure. This also includes emissions from maintenance, repairs, replacements, deconstruction or demolition, waste treatment, and disposal. These impacts are covered by modules A1-A5, B1-B5, and C1-C4, encompassing all material-related emissions.

Figure 1-1. Information modules and life cycle stages of civil engineering works⁶

Source: Ramboll, based on EN 15643:2021

⁴Kraka Advisory. (2023). 'Femern Bælt-forbindelsens opdaterede CO2-regnskab: Ingen klimagevinst i tunnelens levetid'

⁵ Finish Ministry of Finance. (2023). 'Suurten ratahankkeiden rahoituksen ja investointimahdollisuuksien selvitys'.

⁶The A0 phase refers to the early design and planning stage, where critical decisions are made regarding design, materials, and construction methods, as well as how they will be procured. A 'whole-life' carbon assessment takes into account modules A-C. There is also a D module, which covers potential benefits and loads beyond the system boundaries. Hence, a full LCA includes impacts from module A-D.

1.2 Study aim, approach and scope

The aim of this report is to present an overview of the approaches of Nordic infrastructure bodies to addressing the climate impacts of road and rail projects. From this overview, the report will showcase good practices and deliver recommendations for the infrastructure bodies to implement measures at the intersection of public procurement and LCAs to reduce the embodied carbon of infrastructure projects.

Study approach

The study was conducted using a series of different data sources and validation efforts, to ensure that the findings accurately demonstrate the means for addressing and reducing embodied carbon in Nordic transport infrastructure.

The research process is illustrated in Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-2. Research process

First, an assessment sheet was developed to specify the aspects of interest to the study and to support consistency in the data collected for each country. To establish a comprehensive overview of the topic and ongoing efforts in the Nordic countries, the infrastructure project planning processes, the legislative framework and enabling conditions, and potential developments (learnings, capacity building, mainstreaming and coordination, harmonisation measures) were also included in the template.

Country-specific data was collected in two ways, namely in-depth desk research and interviews with stakeholder representatives. First, information was gathered through in-depth desk research for each country. Sources included scientific and grey literature on the governance, planning, and procurement of transport infrastructure in the Nordic countries, as well as guidelines and reports from the national infrastructure bodies. This was complemented by a series

of interviews with national representatives and expert stakeholders. Using the collected information, country analyses were conducted to build an overview of existing approaches to address embodied carbon in Nordic transport infrastructure projects. These country analyses formed the basis for the cross-country analysis and comparison of similarities and differences in embodied carbon management across the Nordic countries, as well as identifying good practices.

Furthermore, two reference group meetings were arranged with representatives from the national infrastructure bodies and sector experts to further contextualise and validate the findings. These in-depth conversations provided insights and nuanced perspectives on the practice of embodied carbon assessment in infrastructure projects.

Scope of the study

This study focuses on embodied carbon from road and rail transport infrastructure within the Nordic countries.

Hereafter, 'transport infrastructure' and 'infrastructure' will be used interchangeably when considering road and rail infrastructure.

The scope of this work is limited to national transport infrastructure. Municipal and local infrastructure projects are not considered in this study. However, responsibilities for transport infrastructure in the Nordic countries are divided between various national, regional, and local actors. While regional and local actors often handle specific tasks related to the infrastructure system, this study does not delve into the interactions between these different levels of governance unless specifically mentioned. This exclusion is intended to simplify the analysis and maintain a clear focus on national projects.

This study focuses on embodied carbon emissions, and more specifically the influence of high-impact materials like steel and cement. However, it is important to recognise that, currently, assessments related to embodied carbon vary and may not always cover all the life cycle stages required by LCA, nor are they as systematic and guided. Embodied carbon assessments can be conducted somewhat more lightly (compared to a full LCA) and can be instructed on a case-by-case basis. When comparing results, it is important to note that the level of maturity of calculating embodied carbon varies by country, and the approaches can differ. Additionally, methodologies, guidelines, tools, and databases also vary by country. These factors influence who can perform the calculations. Still, carbon assessments play a critical role in integrating and appropriately reflecting climate considerations within the decision-making process in infrastructure projects.

Report outline

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 provides an overview of the transport infrastructure management process in the Nordic countries, including the main actors involved and the relevant planning phases. Chapter 3 highlights how embodied carbon is currently considered in Nordic infrastructure. The role of tools in addressing embodied carbon will then be highlighted, by focusing on both EIA (Chapter 4) and public procurement (Chapter 5). Chapter 6 contains a summary and suggested actions based on the findings identified during this study.

Additionally, throughout the report, frontrunning initiatives across the Nordics will be introduced to provide practical examples for comparison and learning. These good practices and innovative pilot projects also carry other non-emissions-related benefits, such as improved material circularity and health benefits through less noise and air pollution. Such co-benefits are important to acknowledge in funding decisions for low-carbon measures.

2. Transport infrastructure management in the Nordics

This section sets the scene by providing an overview of the transport infrastructure actors and management process in the Nordics. It gives a background to Nordic transport infrastructure management and describes key elements of this process relating to embodied carbon in each country, highlighting similarities and differences between them.

2.1 Complexity in transport infrastructure planning and management

The Nordic countries have largely similar processes for planning transport infrastructure, but differences exist in terms of decision-making structure and roles and mandates of different actors. Transport infrastructure development is guided by national policies and legislation through a comprehensive set of regulations, processes, and steering mechanisms (Global Infrastructure Hub & Ramboll, 2021) While varying in size and population density, the Nordic countries also share many of the main conditions that frame road and rail infrastructure development and management, including skills and capacities, raw material resources, and construction methods and techniques.

Transport infrastructure management is characterised by high complexity, with interlinkages between a variety of actors, who have different mandates and operate at different governance levels, policy goals, and regulations. This results in numerous potential trade-offs (e.g. safety vs efficiency, environmental impact vs accessibility and expansion) and high ambiguity regarding requirements and responsibilities, necessitating attention to various, often conflicting, goals. In

general, the main objective of national transport infrastructure management is to develop and maintain a socio-economically efficient transport system that improves the accessibility of both people and goods.

The complexity of transport infrastructure management is set to grow as climate goals become increasingly stringent across the Nordics. As further highlighted in Chapter 3, the Nordic countries aim for climate neutrality or significant reductions by mid-century, in line with the Paris Agreement. These objectives are passed down to ministries and authorities, requiring infrastructure bodies to actively support climate change mitigation. As a result, ministries, government authorities, and infrastructure bodies must align their decisions and actions with these targets to reduce overall GHG emissions. Considering embodied carbon in transport infrastructure, analytical methods and tools must specifically take into account these emissions throughout the entire infrastructure management process (from planning to construction and maintenance) and ensure such considerations are included in decision-making.

2.2 Roles and responsibilities of Nordic transport infrastructure actors

To understand how climate ambitions are applied to transport infrastructure planning, the roles and responsibilities of national actors must be outlined. Planning transport infrastructure is a shared responsibility, involving various actors who manage different phases of a project. Additionally, the governance structure and the roles of these actors vary across countries.

The main actors in transport infrastructure planning are organised into three groups; 1) ministries, 2) supervising entities, and 3) infrastructure bodies. The supervising entities include authorities in charge of regulating and monitoring the transport sector, along those involved in the EIA approval process. The third group includes both governmental entities and state-owned enterprises, to capture the varying governance models across the Nordics. Table 2-1 describes the roles of each actor group as defined in this report.

The most significant differences in governance models are seen at the level of infrastructure bodies. In all countries, the ministry has overall responsibility for the national infrastructure system and guides the relevant bodies in implementing the politically determined transport infrastructure programmes. All Nordic countries then have authorities serving as regulatory and supervisory authorities, although their precise responsibilities and goals vary slightly. The administration and management of national roads and railways are delegated to infrastructure bodies, which for this study include government entities as well as state-owned enterprises. The main actors in each country are outlined in Table 2-2. **This grouping should be considered as a guide. In reality, it is more complex, and the division is not necessarily as clear-cut.**

One clear difference between the Nordic countries is the division of responsibility over road and rail infrastructure. In Finland and Sweden there is one central infrastructure body that plans, constructs, and manages both road and rail infrastructure, whereas in Denmark and Norway this is split between different actors, and includes both state-owned enterprises and governmental administrative units. In Norway, two separate actors are active in the field of road infrastructure: the Norwegian Public Roads Administration (NPRA, Norwegian: Statens Vegvesen), which falls under the remit of the Ministry of Transport and is responsible for planning, construction, and management of the national road network and Nye Veier, with a specific mandate to develop and manage major highways. Iceland does not currently have any public railroad, and thus the analysis in Iceland only covers road infrastructure.

Another important difference is the level of independence of the infrastructure bodies vis-à-vis the national transport ministries. Based on their public administration model, the infrastructure bodies in Denmark, Norway and Iceland are tied to the relevant ministry, whereas their counterparts in Finland and Sweden are separate entities and thus experience a higher degree of autonomy (Lundgren et al., 2023; Wenander, 2022). As such, the ministries have more direct influence on transport policies and transport infrastructure development in Denmark, Norway and Iceland (Wenander, 2022).

Finally, responsibilities for regional and local transport, as well as overlapping infrastructure, vary among countries. As this study only looks at the overarching approaches to considering embodied carbon in national transport infrastructure, the division of responsibilities on projects at the intersection between national entities at regional and local levels will not be described further.

Table 2-1. Categorisation of main actors and responsibilities in national transport infrastructure

Type of actor	General responsibility
Ministry	Overall planning of national infrastructure developments, often through National Infrastructure Plans.
Supervising entities (authorities)	Sectoral supervising entities - regulating and monitoring the transport sector, including the approval infrastructure plans.
	EIA regulatory entities - approval of EIAs.
Infrastructure bodies (e.g. authorities or state-owned enterprises)	Processes relating to the development, management and administration of national rail and road networks.

Table 2-2. Main actors in Nordic transport infrastructure planning

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Ministry	Denmark's Ministry of Transport	Finland's Ministry of Transport and Communications	Iceland's Ministry of Infrastructure	Norway's Ministry of Transport	Sweden's Ministry of Rural Affairs and Infrastructure
Sectoral supervisory authorities	Civil Aviation and Railway Authority	- Finnish Transport and Communications Agency (Traficom) - ELY Centres ⁷	Icelandic Transport Authority	- Road Supervisory Authority - Rail Supervisory Authority - County Governor	- Swedish Transport Agency ⁸ - The County Administrative Boards ⁹ - Swedish Transport Administration
EIA regulatory entities	Danish Environmental Protection Agency	ELY Centres	Icelandic National Planning Agency	Governmental body: e.g. municipalities for local projects, county for regional projects.	County Administrative Board (CAB)

⁷ Centres for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment are divided depending on the responsibilities. ELY Centres operate under the guidance of the FTIA. For road projects, both FTIA and ELY Centres can order planning and construction. In railway projects, FTIA is always responsible for ordering planning and construction.

⁸ The Swedish Transport Agency is responsible for the regulation of road, rail, air and sea transport, rather than transport infrastructure.

⁹ There are 21 County Administrative Boards in Sweden; one for each county.

Table 2-2. Main actors in Nordic transport infrastructure planning (continued)

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Road infrastructure body	Danish Road Directorate (DRD)	Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency (FTIA) ELY Centres	Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration (IRCA)	- Norwegian Public Roads Administration (NPRA, Statens Vegvesen) - 'Nye Veier' *	Swedish Transport Administration (STA)
Rail infrastructure body	'Banedanmark' *		N/A (currently no public railway in Iceland)	'Bane NOR' *	

* = state-owned enterprise.

2.3 The infrastructure project planning process

Across the Nordics, planning takes place via a step-by-step and highly formalised process, with infrastructure bodies as central actors. A streamlined and simplified outline of Nordic infrastructure project planning is presented in Figure 2-1, including the main actors involved in each step of the process.

However, when and how different actors are involved also differs depending on project size and contractual model. For instance, in design-build contracts, contractors are engaged earlier in the process compared to traditional design-bid-build models where the design and construction is done separately.

In most Nordic countries, the infrastructure bodies lead and coordinate the infrastructure planning process.

To capture variation between countries, the full boxes show planning phases where actors are involved or carbon efforts implemented in all of the Nordic countries, while the boxes with dotted borders indicate coverage in one or more countries.

However, alongside the decision-making of infrastructure bodies, new major infrastructure projects are generally assessed on a case-by-case basis by governmental bodies, meaning such projects require national government approval to proceed with construction, as shown in the table below.

Phases in the Nordic infrastructure planning process

The first phase in the planning process is to identify the need for infrastructure development to deliver on the national transport goals – e.g. safety, transport efficiency and accessibility, reduced GHG emissions from the transport sector – and assessing and comparing transport infrastructure projects. In the Nordics, this is done through National Transport Plans. The plans specify the strategic framework and investment plan for the transport infrastructure systems for the next 10-15 years and are revised at shorter intervals (3-5 years). The governments (Ministries of Transport) formally propose the plans, which are then subject to parliamentary approval. The infrastructure bodies assist with preparation of the plan, with different levels of involvement depending on the country. In Sweden, for example, the infrastructure body (Swedish Transportation Administration) is mandated by the government to develop a proposal, which serves as a basis for the formal proposal from the government.

A cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is often conducted to identify and find the most socio-economically favourable projects and inform decision-making leading up to the plan.

Figure 2-1. Simplified outline of infrastructure project planning in the Nordic countries

Source: Ramboll

Table 2-3. Final approval decisions on infrastructure projects across the Nordic countries

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Final approval decision on infrastructure project	Major infrastructure projects often require approval by the Danish Parliament, especially in the case of public funding or changes to existing laws.	The Finnish Transport and Communications Agency (Traficom) makes an approval decision. Major projects require additional governmental approval.	Final proposal submitted to the Icelandic parliament Althingi for debate in the form of a parliamentary Resolution.	Large projects are approved for construction and prioritised through the National Transport Plan of the Ministry of Transport. Compliance with national policies is checked by Statsforvalteren.	The National Transport Administration provides final approval. For specific large projects, government approval is required.

Shadow carbon costs can be used in the CBA to reflect the social and environmental costs of emissions, ensuring more accurate and comprehensive economic appraisals.

The second phase is the feasibility study, which involves a thorough assessment of potential infrastructure projects and associated costs, technical needs, environmental impacts, and economic benefits and risks. These assessments, commissioned by the infrastructure bodies, demonstrate preliminary technical and traffic solutions for the road or railway and the principles underlying the prevention of environmental impact. These studies help to determine whether the project should proceed to the planning phase, through approval by national or regional supervising authorities.

This is followed by the preliminary design phase, in which a more detailed plan is developed that describes how the project will be implemented and how negative impacts will be mitigated. This also includes determining the approximate location of the road or railway.

Next, the detailed design is specified to ensure that all aspects of the project are technically feasible and compliant with national standards. Here, architectural design and technical specifications are prepared to inform the construction.

The construction phase normally begins with laying out the procurement criteria and agreeing on the project terms and final specifications with a contractor. The contractors' involvement might occur earlier in the process, depending on the procurement model. As described further in Chapter 5, procurement is a powerful tool for reducing embodied carbon from transport infrastructure.

Finally, operations and maintenance of national transport infrastructure fall under the responsibility of the infrastructure bodies. In the case of maintenance and redevelopment works, whether it is done by the infrastructure body or procured on the market will depend on the scope of the effort.

Box 2.1 Shadow carbon pricing

One potential avenue for better integrating climate considerations in decision making processes is so called shadow carbon pricing, where GHG emissions are accounted for and expressed in monetary value.

When assessing infrastructure projects, shadow carbon pricing is used to account for potential carbon costs over the project's life cycle. By incorporating this price into the analyses, decision-makers can evaluate how carbon emissions impact the overall viability of a project, encouraging low-carbon alternatives and reducing long-term climate risks.

Most Nordic countries use shadow carbon pricing as part of their socio-economic/cost-benefit analyses. As a result, projects with higher GHG emissions have a higher negative shadow carbon cost, increasing the overall project cost.

In Finland, the cost of carbon is considered as part of project appraisals, while in Sweden, the relation between project costs and CO₂ emissions is estimated outside of the contracting procedure. Meanwhile, in Denmark and Norway, carbon pricing schemes have been integrated into the contracting procedure. This approach allows contractors with lower emissions to benefit from reduced final costs of their offering. A Danish assessment of the pilot testing in asphalt projects, showed that by considering shadow costs of carbon, the investment in low carbon alternatives makes economically sense (Vejdirektoratet, 2019).

3. Embodied carbon considerations in Nordic infrastructure

This section highlights how embodied carbon is currently considered in Nordic infrastructure. First, Section 3.1 will set out embodied carbon targets and their monitoring strategies, to provide an overview of goals and sectoral performance on embodied carbon across the Nordic countries. Section 3.2 will then introduce embodied carbon considerations at project level, highlighting different approaches taken by infrastructure bodies.

3.1 Embodied carbon targets and performance monitoring

Table 3-1. Summary of embodied carbon targets and performance management for transport infrastructure

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Embodied carbon targets	Road: no quantified targets defined Rail: 20-30% reduction in total, covers embodied carbon.	No quantified targets defined.	No quantified targets defined.	Each actor has individual goals that are currently being discussed and updated, generally cover embodied carbon.	Climate neutral by 2040 covers embodied carbon.
Monitoring of embodied carbon performance	Road: Project-specific data (for major projects), no aggregated data Rail: Under development as part of implementing CSRD requirements.	Project-specific data is collected and available, no aggregated data.	Not monitored.	Varies between the actors, but in general only project-specific data is collected and available. Aggregated data is available for Nye Veier and NPRA.	Project-specific data is collected and available. Aggregated data is available upon request.
Current embodied carbon performance	Project-specific reductions No current tracking and overview of portfolio level.	Project-specific reductions No current overview and overview of portfolio level.	No current tracking and overview.	Project-specific reductions Portfolio-level tracking and overview varies between actors.	Project-specific reductions Portfolio-level tracking and overview show reductions have been achieved, but unclear whether reductions are in line with target levels.

Emissions reduction strategies in the Nordics are guided by overall national climate goals, enshrined in law in all countries. All Nordic countries seek to achieve climate neutrality or reductions in line with the Paris Agreement by the middle of the century¹⁰. These targets cascade down to national ministries and authorities and obligate the infrastructure bodies to promote climate change mitigation efforts. Ministries, government authorities and infrastructure bodies must consider the climate targets when designing and making decisions on actions that influence overall GHG emissions.

These general reduction targets are, however, not well placed to drive low-carbon performance at the sectoral level of transport infrastructure. It is not a straightforward exercise to derive sector-specific targets from generic targets, meaning that the overarching national targets are limited in their ability to inform decision-making at infrastructure administration and management level (i.e. the infrastructure bodies). Furthermore, these targets only cover territorial (production-based)

emissions and do not consider trade-adjusted emissions, i.e. consumption-based emissions.¹¹ As a result, emissions associated with the production and transportation of imported materials used in Nordic infrastructure are not part of national emissions targets.

Embodied carbon reduction strategies

Focusing instead on the specific strategies of the infrastructure bodies and, in particular, embodied carbon targets for transport infrastructure, a differentiated picture emerges regarding ambitions and stated goals.

Specifically, Sweden has quantitative targets covering embodied emissions, implemented through the Swedish Transport Administration (STA). The aim is to achieve climate neutrality across all construction, operational, and maintenance activities by 2040, five years before the national climate target set in 2045, with sub-targets for reductions compared to baseline year 2015 (Swedish Transport Administration, 2023).

Box 3.1. Good practice: Setting (sub-)targets for Swedish transport infrastructure

To reach the climate neutrality goal by 2040, the Swedish Transport Administration has set the following sub-targets covering all emissions related to road and railway infrastructure activities compared to 2015 (Scope 1-3):

- 2020 - 15 percent
- 2025 - 30 percent
- 2030 - 60 percent
- 2035 - 80 percent

An impact assessment (Uppenberg et al., 2015) conducted during the preparatory efforts for establishing the climate targets showed that the reduction targets can be achieved at no or limited additional costs (both for material purchases and for project development), with cost savings through increased resource efficiency and reduced greenhouse gas emissions often going hand in hand.

Additionally, a sectoral roadmap developed by the Fossil-Free Sweden (2024) government initiative further highlights the required measures in transport infrastructure construction (as part of the construction and civil engineering sector) to reach the established targets.

¹⁰ Denmark, Finland, Iceland and Sweden aim to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 at the latest. By then, Norway seeks to become a 'low-emission society', defined as a society where GHG emissions, based on the best available scientific knowledge, global emission trends and national circumstances, have been reduced to avert the adverse impacts of global warming, as described in the Paris Agreement.

¹¹ Consumption-based emissions are calculated by including GHG emissions from the production of imports and removing GHG emissions from the production of exports to the total territorial emissions.

Norway and **Denmark** also have targets for the transport infrastructure sector, although these vary in terms of coverage and ambition level depending on the different infrastructure bodies. The three Norwegian infrastructure bodies generally follow the national targets (territorial emissions) in terms of reduction levels. Thus, embodied carbon from imported materials used in construction has a lower priority than the territorial emissions levels that should be reported to the Ministry of Transport. While the Norwegian infrastructure bodies also have targets on embodied carbon, they lack a mandate on this. In Denmark, reduction targets are in place covering all emissions from rail infrastructure (20–30% reduction until 2030), but no clear targets exist for road infrastructure.

Finland and **Iceland**¹² currently have no defined targets for reducing embodied emissions from rail or road infrastructure. In Finland, however, the FTIA has embedded sustainability into its procurement policy directives and has established several qualitative objectives. This includes the identification and implementation of circular economy criteria in maintenance works, which are set to promote the reduction of virgin materials and aggregates. Additionally, the FTIA has joined a 'green deal agreement' on emission-free worksites, aiming to reduce emissions and promote low-emissions approaches at construction sites. See Box 5.3 for more details.

Monitoring and reporting progress towards embodied carbon targets

Generally, across the Nordics, monitoring and reporting is conducted at project level, and for most of the Nordic countries, aggregated information is lacking at portfolio level. The focus of monitoring and reporting life cycle GHG emissions data is concentrated on larger projects or pilot projects, focusing on how the use of low-carbon materials and solutions has led to reductions. While such information is useful for increasing knowledge at the reduction potential of specific innovations, the absence of summary data limits the understanding of carbon performance and emissions hotspots across the transport infrastructure project portfolio.

There are differences in reporting requirements between infrastructure bodies that are government entities and those that are state-owned companies. Unlike government entities, state-owned companies – BaneDanmark (Danish rail), Nye Veier (Norwegian road) and Bane NOR – all fall under the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS); the reporting standards introduced as part of the EU Corporate

Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).¹³ The ESRS includes mandatory disclosure of climate impacts from activities, including materials-related emissions and other embodied carbon sources. Additionally, Norway's Environmental Information Act (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2003) led to further development of systems and methods to facilitate this disclosure of environmental impact. Bane NOR is not yet obliged to report under the CSRD but has chosen to report according to the new standards starting from this year.

Nye Veier already reports emissions according to GHG protocol Scope 1–3¹⁴ (Nye Veier, 2023). However, monitoring and reporting processes are likely to improve further as Nye Veier fully aligns with the CSRD. Finally, BaneDanmark is currently exploring ways to align its collecting and handling of embodied carbon data with the new requirements.

In Sweden, projects that require a carbon assessment have their early-stage calculations compared to the climate documentation provided at project finalisation (known as project climate declarations). As such, the Swedish Transport Administration can analyse actual carbon performance against the carbon assessment conducted at the start of a project, which supports an improved understanding of uncertainties in early-stage carbon assessments, while learnings can help prevent misinterpretations of results and faulty decision-making. While proving a good example, the database is restricted to internal use and cannot be accessed by stakeholders to examine and compare climate impacts across projects.

Finland and Denmark do also collect information from carbon assessments, but not at a detailed level. Furthermore, the results are not systematically used to guide and improve future activities. For these countries, post-project verification does not currently appear to be in place, but action is being taken. For instance, in Finland, the guidance for verification and collection of emissions data during the construction phase is currently under development. In Denmark, the Danish Road Directorate is currently planning to compare actual emissions from the construction phase with the assessments done in the earlier project phases. This would apply to all projects not yet completed. In Norway, while there is post-project verification, the link to future projects can be improved upon.

To sum up, Nordic countries are advancing climate neutrality targets that integrate emissions reduction into their transport infrastructure sectors. Monitoring and reporting of embodied emissions remain project-based, with limited aggregated data across national portfolios.

¹² In Iceland, the upcoming long-term National Transport Plan 2024–2038 is intended to include provisions on emissions reductions from construction and from the operation and maintenance of transport infrastructure. The details of these provisions were not known at the time of this publication.

¹³ Directive (EU) 2022/2464.

¹⁴ Common classification of GHG emissions established by the GHG Protocol. Scope 1 includes direct emissions from a company's own activities; Scope 2 covers indirect emissions from purchased electricity or heat and Scope 3 encompasses all other indirect emissions, including, for example, emissions from materials extraction and production in the value chain, employee commuting, and product use.

Box 3.2. Good practice: Denmark, Sweden and Norway are advancing sustainable road construction through innovative pilot projects.

Denmark's initiatives focus on road recycling and climate-friendly asphalt to reduce CO₂ emissions and enhance sustainability and cost efficiency. The E 45 highway project used recycling technology, cutting emissions by over 50% and halving project time (World Highways, 2024). Furthermore, Denmark's adoption of climate-friendly asphalt since 2020 is projected to reduce emissions by up to 616,000 tonnes by 2037, aligning with broader environmental objectives and serving as a model for sustainable construction practices (State of Green, 2019). Additionally, Denmark introduced a CO₂ pricing model in **ten pilot projects**, rewarding contractors who surpass sustainability targets and reinforcing its climate goals. As part of this, contractors deliver product-specific EPDs at the end of the project, which will be compared to the initial EPDs, after which contractors are to receive a bonus-malus based on their performance (Ios, 2023).

In **Sweden**, E10 Kauppinen-Kiruna project is one of **eight pilot projects** to cut CO₂ throughout road planning, procurement and construction phases. Through the project, the objective is to achieve a minimum 50% reduction in the project's climate footprint through systematic, interdisciplinary efforts fostering innovation across various technological domains to discover environmentally friendly solutions (Trafikverket, 2024b).

In 2023, the **Norwegian** Ministry of Transport announced funding for **ten new pilot projects** aimed at developing emission-free construction sites exploring practical measures to reduce GHG emissions stemming from construction machinery such as excavators, wheel loaders, and dump trucks. With 65 million NOK allocated to reduce emissions through projects like E18 Vestkorridoren, which employs electric machinery and charging infrastructure. Norway's pilots promote operational experience with electric technologies, aiming for sustainable emission cuts in the transport sector.

Together, these countries' pilots illustrate scalable approaches to decarbonising transport infrastructure construction.

3.2 Approaches to carbon assessments

Carbon assessment as a concept

When conducting carbon assessments, consistency is key to integrating and appropriately reflecting on climate considerations within the decision-making process in infrastructure projects. Throughout the project planning process, carbon assessments can be utilised to compare solutions and facilitate decisions that promote low-carbon practices.

Figure 3-1. Building blocks for consistent carbon assessments

Source: Ramboll

Consistent carbon assessment can be set up through 1) standardised methods and processes uniformly applied across the industry, 2) functional and standardised calculation tools, and 3) access to accurate emissions data, as also highlighted in Figure 3-1.

Carbon assessment in transport infrastructure

In the Nordic countries, carbon assessment through the use of LCA tools is emphasised and implemented to measure and understand the climate impacts of transport infrastructure. The practices for each country are summarised in table 3-2.

Carbon assessments in transport infrastructure design and development remain unregulated at national level across all Nordic countries, with no mandatory provisions in place. However, infrastructure bodies in Denmark (road), Norway (road) and Sweden (road and rail) set assessment requirements for projects above certain values (Danish Ministry of Transport & Danish Road Directorate, 2023; Norwegian Public Roads Administration, n.d.; Swedish Transport Administration, 2023). A new guideline for Finland that requires carbon calculations for all projects above EUR 2 million has been published, but has not yet been fully implemented (Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency, 2023).

Through the efforts of these Nordic infrastructure bodies, carbon assessments have emerged as common practice across the Nordic countries. However, as seen in the table above, the modules covered in the assessments differ between countries. This is also the case regarding the consideration of emissions caused by land-use change. Such differences in scope and system boundaries make it difficult to compare assessment results across countries.

Differences are observed regarding project phases where carbon assessments are conducted, both between the Nordic countries and between road and rail actors within countries. In Denmark, road projects implement carbon assessments for all phases, whereas no common practice has been established for rail projects. In Iceland, Norway and Sweden, carbon assessments are generally done in all project phases, while in Finland it is concentrated in the detailed design and construction phase for both road and rail. The goal in Finland is to extend carbon assessments to all design phases and to standardise the integration of carbon considerations into project management procedures.

Table 3-2. Summary of methods, tools and data used for carbon assessments of transport infrastructure

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Regulatory framework	Not regulated in national legislation.	Not regulated in national legislation.	Not regulated in national legislation.	Not regulated in national legislation.	Not regulated in national legislation.
Applicability of carbon assessment	Required for road projects above DKK 10 million (approx. EUR 1.3 million). Common practice for all road and rail projects.	Required for projects that require project appraisal (generally projects above EUR 2 million). Common practice for other road and rail projects.	All projects included in national transport infrastructure plan.	NPRA (road): required for all projects above NOK 51 million (approx. EUR 4.5 million). Common practice for other road and rail projects.	Required for all projects above SEK 50 million (approx. EUR 4.4 million). Common practice for other road and rail projects.
Carbon assessment conducted in project phases	For road infrastructure, all phases for applicable projects. For rail, no general practice in place.	All phases	All phases	All phases	All phases
LCA modules covered in carbon assessment	A1-A5, B4, C1-C4, D	A1-A5, B4 Indirectly, phase C, to the extent that the replaced parts need to be transported to disposal.	A1-A5, B3-B5	A1-A5, B1-B6	A1-A5, B1-B5

Table 3-2. Summary of methods, tools and data used for carbon assessments of transport infrastructure (continued)

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
<p>Carbon assessment tools</p> <p>National guidelines/methodology for carbon assessment</p>	<p>'InfraLCA' is most common, but no mandatory tool.</p> <p>Methodology has been developed for using InfraLCA.</p>	<p>No mandatory tool</p> <p>National guidelines have been developed for carbon assessments of any projects.</p>	<p>'LOKI' (Lífsferilsgreining og kolefnisspor innviðaframkvæmda) to be used for projects where carbon assessment is required.</p> <p>Expected completed rollout by beginning of 2025.</p>	<p>'VegLCA' must be used for NPRA road projects where carbon assessment is required, otherwise no mandatory tool. Methodology has been developed for specific tools (VegLCA, other assessment tools). Other tools include 'NV-GHG-3-1', used by Nye Veier.</p>	<p>'Klimatkalkyl' must be used for projects where carbon assessment is required, otherwise no mandatory tool.</p> <p>Methodology has been developed for using Klimatkalkyl</p> <p>Other tools include 'Geokalkyl'.</p>
<p>Consideration of land -use change</p> <p>Impacts on carbon balance from land-use change</p>	<p>Currently not part of carbon assessment.</p>	<p>Currently not part of carbon assessment.</p>	<p>Currently not part of carbon assessment.</p>	<p>Included in most common tools used for both road and rail.</p>	<p>Included in the main tool Klimatkalkyl.</p>
<p>Product data sources</p> <p>Generic material data</p>	<p>Provided in InfraLCA, from several databases.</p>	<p>National emissions database (co2data.fi), from several databases. Updated in 2023 with data for infrastructure construction.</p>	<p>National database, other Nordic databases.</p>	<p>National EPD database (EPD Norge), other databases.</p>	<p>Provided in Klimatkalkyl, from several databases.</p>
<p>Product data sources</p> <p>Product-specific data</p>	<p>EPDs must be collected and used for projects above DKK 5 million (approx. EUR 0.7 million). Requirements are continuously being revised as knowledge improves.</p>	<p>Based on EPD for infrastructure construction in national emissions database.</p>	<p>From material EPDs.</p>	<p>From material EPDs.</p>	<p>From verified EPDs or equivalent level of data reliability.</p>

Box 3.3. Good practice: Integrated cost and CO2 calculation systems in Finland and Sweden

In Finland, the **Ihku CO2 calculation service** is part of the Infrastructure Cost Management System (Ihku) alliance project, which aims to create a comprehensive and open-access cost management solution for various infrastructure projects in Finland. The system is designed to meet future needs and challenges by providing timely and reliable cost data for infrastructure projects.

Emissions calculation, a key feature of the Ihku system, is integrated into the cost estimation process. It is based on CO2 data from the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and integrated with the CO2 calculation method by FTIA. Users can automatically calculate the emissions of projects and construction components by adding items to the cost estimate. Emissions data coverage is continually improved as SYKE updates its databases. Additionally, users have the flexibility to modify emissions coefficients and add their own data.

The Ihku system also supports the generation of emissions reports, which can be used for various reporting purposes, including integration with tools like Power BI. The development of the Ihku system is guided by regular stakeholder feedback, ensuring it meets the needs of end users and administrators. The Ihku system is based on the Finnish Infra Classification System and will support the entire infrastructure sector, enabling an evolving and comprehensive database for better cost estimation and awareness.

In Sweden, the **Geokalkyl tool**, developed by STA in 2015, supports the planning process by generating combined cost and GHG calculations of road and rail projects. More specifically, it helps in the early-stage decision on where to locate infrastructure assets, i.e. comparing different line options and choosing corridors. The tool combines geographical data, soil maps, climate zone, surrounding assets, protected areas, real estate, etc. Results are presented visually with generated bars (per 20 m sections) along the line on a 3D map, via Excel tables and optional charts.

By analysing different options, designers can adjust the project layout to reduce costs, improve mass balance, or lower climate impact. This detailed insight also helps in identifying where further investigations are needed during the planning process. The Geokalkyl tool has so far been voluntary to use.

Carbon assessment tools and methods

In general, carbon assessments in Nordic transport infrastructure have been guided by the choice or development of assessment tools and focused on developing methodologies for the use of these tools. Using this approach, improvement efforts are made by updating the specific tools to ensure more precise calculations and alignment with new standards.

A couple of noticeable exceptions are found, such as in Finland, where the model has shifted to instead develop general methodological guidelines for conducting carbon assessments. In 2023, the FTIA introduced a method for whole-life carbon assessment of infrastructure projects (Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency, 2023). The guidelines detail the method for conducting carbon assessment. The Ihku cost and CO2 calculation system (see box above) provides most of the information on emissions linked to A1-A5, but sector professionals remain free to choose the tool they prefer as long as they follow the prescribed method. The

FTIA has also created comprehensive training materials and a website to support the implementation of carbon assessment and carbon management in design, and aims to update this regularly as their knowledge increases. Actors in Finland have also developed an integrated cost management and emissions data system, allowing for automatic calculation of emissions alongside costs (see Box 3.3).

Furthermore, in Norway and Denmark, efforts are underway to harmonise carbon assessments between the infrastructure bodies. In Denmark, for instance, the Danish Road Directorate scheduled a workshop with other organisations under the Ministry of Transport, to discuss the possibility of aligning methods for carbon assessment. This could be done either through the development of a common tool with the same database, or by aligning with the methodological approach, to allow for a shared database to be developed while working with different tools. In Norway, as further highlighted in Box 3.4, harmonisation guidelines are established as a collaborative effort between the three main infrastructure actors in Norway (NPRA, Nye Veier, and Bane NOR) and industry stakeholders during the 'Harmonisation day' sector initiative.

Box 3.4. Good practice: Active collaboration to harmonise carbon assessments between Norwegian actors

On 22 May 2024 the fourth version of the Norwegian event 'Harmoniseringsdagen' (harmonisation day) took place with representatives from Bane NOR, Nye Veier and NPRA, as well as entrepreneurs, consultants and other stakeholders in the Norwegian infrastructure industry. During the event, the first version of new guidance on carbon assessments of infrastructure projects was launched. The guidance serves tool developers and can be considered general methodological guidelines.

This annual day of collaboration is marked by the sharing of responsibilities to strengthen decarbonisation efforts, gathering the whole industry to discuss and share knowledge. 'Harmoniseringsdagen' has improved sector-wide understanding and streamlined the process for agreeing on carbon assessment methods and practices. Additionally, it provides a sense of security and motivation for continuous innovation among industry actors, knowing that agreed-upon efforts will be followed up at future harmonisation day events.

Carbon assessment data management

In terms of data on product or service-related emissions factors, all countries have some type of national database for construction products and activities but none offer open databases detailing the carbon performance of ongoing infrastructure projects. The input to these databases comes from multiple sources and open emissions inventories. However, no country has an open national database with detailed information about the carbon performance of ongoing or finalised infrastructure projects, split, for example, by materials of life cycle module.

Finland is leading the way, as the Finnish Environmental Institute has developed an open-access national building and construction emissions database,¹⁵ which allows for integration into digital assessment tools.

For Norway, Denmark and Sweden, the databases have been developed within the carbon assessment tools themselves. While these databases are comprehensive and fit-for-purpose

in the respective tools, this approach makes it more difficult to access the data and use it in other applications. In Denmark, it is likely that there will be a separation between the database and LCA tool (InfraLCA). This also opens up the possibility of collaboration on the database with other organisations. In Norway, there are initiatives to develop a separate national database, but discussions are ongoing regarding ownership and development responsibilities.

Data from the national databases is particularly useful in the early stages, whereas in later stages more detailed and product-specific data can be used. For projects where carbon assessments must be made, the use of product-specific emissions data (EPDs or similar verified data) is required in Sweden, Denmark and Norway.

The increased availability of EPDs appears to have improved the accuracy of the carbon calculations. While challenges remain in terms of collecting and using reliable EPD data, particularly for innovative and low-carbon materials, the robustness and comparability of EPDs will likely increase further with the implementation of the EU Construction Product Regulation.¹⁶

¹⁵ See here: <https://www.co2data.fi/>

¹⁶ The revised EU Construction Product Regulation will require that every construction product sold within the EU will need to disclose its Global Warming Potential (GWP), enabling architects, engineers, and developers to take informed decisions for their projects.

Future developments in carbon assessment

In terms of next steps, efforts in the Nordic countries are ongoing to improve carbon assessment methods and input data quality, to produce more reliable and comprehensive emissions calculations.

One such measure is to better account for decreasing carbon sequestration capacity from forests and land converted for transport infrastructure developments. Recent updates to the main tools used in Sweden and Norway have made it possible to take into account land-use change, specifically with regards to peatlands and wetlands, while deforestation has been included since before the 2024 update. However, these impacts are not part of the carbon assessment methods in Denmark, Iceland, or Finland. Advancements are also being made in expanding the carbon assessments to additional phases in the planning process.

Another aspect is the temporal element of infrastructure projects, in which emissions factors (from materials or construction activities) may change significantly between the initial carbon assessments, the start of construction and once the project is finalised. How to accurately calculate climate impacts from projects where construction is expected to start several years in the future is currently being discussed within the Nordic infrastructure bodies, and new methods are being

introduced. The Danish Road Directorate has enhanced their LCA tool (InfraLCA) by integrating climate projections from the Danish Energy Agency, allowing users to adjust emissions factors based on the anticipated construction start year. For example, the Danish Road Directorate has updated their LCA tool (InfraLCA) by integrating climate projections from the Danish Energy Agency. This extension allows users to input the anticipated construction start year, which in turn adjusts the projected emissions according to climate forecasts.

There is currently high interest in applying and integrating digital solutions to improve carbon assessments at early stages of transport infrastructure development. One important area for advancing embodied carbon reductions in transport infrastructure is integrating carbon assessment tools within Building Information Modelling (BIM) software. In essence, BIM helps create 3D models of the physical and functional characteristics of built environments, forming a reliable basis for decisions linked to planning, designing, constructing and managing the buildings and infrastructure. Integrating carbon assessments into BIM software would facilitate rapid and accurate evaluation of the climate impact of transport infrastructure early in the project design phase. This is currently not widespread in the Nordic countries (only Swedish tool Geokalkyl is BIM-compatible), but efforts are underway to advance the combined use of BIM and carbon assessments, for example, the Nordic NordClimpact-collaboration project and the Norwegian initiative KlimaDigital.

Box 3.5 Nordic collaboration on life cycle assessments

With a point of departure in the traditions for political and policy coordination in the Nordic region, i.e. in the Nordic Council of Ministers, the Nordic infrastructure bodies have already made significant steps to maximise the sharing of technical knowledge, best practices and Nordic streamlining of approaches to notable LCA methodologies.

In the cooperative programme NordFoU, established in 2004, the Nordic road authorities have sought to initialise, finance and run research and development projects. NordFoU has conducted several projects related to assessments of road markings, noise calculations and also LCA.

In 2017, three of the five Nordic countries' road authorities (Finland, Norway and Sweden) initiated the NordLCA project. Their goal was to further develop individual LCA tools as well as increase comparability of LCAs across countries, with a predominant focus on carbon emissions via exchanges of knowledge and best practices. At the end of the project in 2020, it resulted in the development of a common LCA guide for the planning, construction and maintenance of both roads and railways, through the use of acknowledged standards, and limiting the flexible interpretation of these standards.

Nordic collaboration on assessing and reducing the climate impact of infrastructure construction was continued through NordLCA+, which built on work that had been done in the NordLCA project. Running between 2021 and 2023, NordLCA+ examined how to further improve LCA procedures, with a particular focus on increasing the usability of tools, linking LCA and Building Information Model (BIM) tools and the use of Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) in LCA.

As of 2024, the same group of Nordic road authorities has launched a new project, NordCLIMPACT, a project striving to promote informed decision-making and incorporate EU taxonomy standards into the work for sustainable infrastructure development. NordCLIMPACT consists of a range of work packages, where one of these will also investigate best practices on public procurement.

4. Embodied carbon in nordic environmental impact assessments

Legislation on transport infrastructure planning and construction covers a broad range of regulations within transport, buildings, and construction and environmental concerns. This section examines environmental provisions in infrastructure development and the integration of embodied carbon into these policies, focusing specifically on EIAs, which are typically conducted during the early stages of infrastructure planning.

4.1 Considering climate impact through EIA

The environmental legislative framework guiding the operations of Nordic infrastructure bodies generally consists of legally binding regulations, as well as interpretive and voluntary practices directed by what is known as soft law (e.g. strategies and guidelines). While the environmental framework specifies requirements, there is room for interpretation in approaches to assessment. Here, soft law tends to play a more significant role, influencing the decision-making process of transport infrastructure development.

In the planning of infrastructure projects, the legislation concerning the assessment of environmental impacts must be observed. Such assessments are often conducted in the feasibility study and/or preliminary design phases. At EU level, environmental assessments of infrastructure projects are guided by the European Union Directives on Strategic Environmental Assessments¹⁷(SEA) and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA).¹⁸

In short, SEAs are required in early-stage decision-making on government plans, programmes and policies to evaluate broader environmental impacts, while EIAs are used to

identify impacts relating specifically to certain projects or activities. As such, the EIA is more directly applicable to the scope of this project. All EU Member States, including Denmark, Finland and Sweden, have transposed the SEA and EIA Directives into national law.¹⁹ The EIA and SEA Directives also apply to Norway and Iceland as part of the European Economic Area agreement,²⁰ meaning the same regulation is in place across the Nordic countries.

The EIA Directive states that the development of, or major modifications to, state railways and major roads are typically subject to an EIA, and that the direct and indirect climate impacts should both be considered. Specifically, the EIA Directive enables the assessment of climate impact on the environment (e.g. in terms of magnitude and nature of greenhouse gas emissions). However, the legislation does not specify precise criteria (on how to precisely assess climate impact) for when EIAs are required, or how they should be conducted. This leaves room for slightly different national applications regarding what projects must undergo an EIA and leaves room for interpretation concerning climate impact.

¹⁷ Directive 2001/42/EC.

¹⁸ Directive 2011/92/EU, as amended by 2014/52/EU.

¹⁹ In all three countries, legal provisions of the SEA and the EIA Directive are included in one national law. Denmark: Environmental Assessment Act (LBK nr 4 af 03/01/2023), Finland: Act on Environmental Impact Assessment Procedure (252/2017), Sweden: The Environmental Code (1998:808).

²⁰ The European Economic Area (EEA) is a region that includes the member countries of the European Union (EU) along with Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway, allowing them to participate in the EU's single market without being EU members.

4.2 Considerations of embodied carbon in EIAs

Table 4-1. Environmental assessment impact procedures in infrastructure projects across the Nordic countries

	Denmark	Finland	Iceland	Norway	Sweden
Actor commissioning the EIA	Danish Road Directorate (DRD), Banedanmark.	Finnish Transport and Infrastructure Agency (FTIA).	Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration (IRCA).	Project developer (e.g. Bane NOR, NPRA).	Swedish Transport Administration (STA).
Actor conducting the EIA	External consultants with support/ in collaboration with the infrastructure bodies.	External consultants with support/ in collaboration with the infrastructure body.	The infrastructure body with support/in collaboration with external consultants.	External consultants with support/ in collaboration with the infrastructure bodies.	External consultants with support/ in collaboration with the infrastructure body.
Actor approving the EIA	Danish Environmental Protection Agency.	ELY centres (Coordinating Authority) approve both the proposal and conducted EIA.	The Icelandic National planning agency.	Approved by responsible authority, e.g. municipalities for local projects, county for regional projects.	County Administrative Board (CAB).
Climate impact in EIA	Integrated into EIA, but no standardised approach.	Integrated into EIA, but no standardised approach.	To be integrated into EIA, but not yet done. Guidelines forthcoming.	Integrated into EIA, but no standardised approach. Norwegian Environment Agency provides guidelines.	Integrated into EIA, but no standardised approach. STA provides guidelines.

Embodied carbon is increasingly being integrated into EIAs across Nordic infrastructure projects. With the Nordics alignment with the EU's EIA Directive, climate impact assessment is often included as part of EIAs conducted on rail and road infrastructure projects. While climate impact in EIAs is often not yet standardised, various Nordic countries (e.g. Finland, Sweden and Norway) have made initial attempts to improve and increase the consistency of assessments through guidelines and tools.

EIAs for Nordic infrastructure projects are typically conducted by external subcontractors (e.g. consultants, other experts). The EIA is conducted following a request by the project developer (e.g. FTIA in Finland, STA in Sweden, NPRA/Nye Veier/Bane NOR in Norway), making the use of external consultants a common practice in this process. The project developer is also the actor responsible for commissioning the assessment. As the EIA is required to obtain approval and/or environmental permits to continue with construction, this assessment is critical to successfully developing an infrastructure project.

The way in which embodied carbon is taken into account varies widely across the Nordic countries, but it is generally already integrated into EIAs, to a large extent. For instance, in Norway, climate impact assessments are often included in EIAs. The NPRA has its own method (V712) for this, which is also mandatory for Nye Veier, and acts as starting point for Bane NOR. The Norwegian Environment Agency (2023) does provide a handbook which should ease general integration of climate impact assessment into EIAs, but GHG emissions are monetised through regular methods in CBAs instead. In Iceland, the Environmental Act and the regulation on environmental assessments of project and plans (nr.1381/2021)²¹ stipulate that climate impact assessments (e.g. GHG emissions and impacts on adaptations to climate change) should be addressed in the EIA process. However, as of now there are no definite plans as to how these impacts should be addressed, though guidelines on this are forthcoming in 2024.

Sweden and Finland seem to be the furthest along when it comes to assessing embodied carbon through EIAs. Through its guidelines, the STA recommends ways in which project developers ought to measure climate impact. While there is currently no standardised method, climate impact assessment is required for an EIA to be approved. More details on the Swedish case can be found in Box 4.1. Meanwhile, in Finland, the ELY Centres, responsible for approving EIAs, can take a more proactive approach by further assessing the identified climate impacts to ascertain their suitability for the specific project.

In Denmark, assessments of climate impact are characterised by a lack of standardised methodological approach with agreed-upon system boundaries (i.e. which life cycle stages to include), resulting in different bases for comparison being

used for the assessments (Christensen et al., 2024). As found by a Danish study, a significant proportion of environmental assessments consider only a small part or phase of a project plan, for example including only the climate impacts from the construction, or more commonly the emissions from vehicles using the infrastructure, and thereby potentially leaving out significant emissions (Christensen et al., 2024).

Approval decisions on EIAs

The consideration of climate impact is generally not a determining factor in infrastructure projects when it comes to the approval decisions on EIAs by the relevant supervising authority. This is a result of gaps in national legislation, which often lacks specificity regarding how the assessment of climate impacts should inform decisions. This allows for interpretation and places the responsibility for considering embodied carbon on individual actors/decision-makers. This was emphasised in a recent environmental assessment of a Danish road project, where the Road Directorate was criticised for not adequately considering embodied carbon as part of the environmental assessments (Andersen, 2024).

Despite this, environmental assessments can be considered as an important tool for long-term climate management.

These assessments hold significant potential for fostering a sustainable society through lower embodied carbon in infrastructure projects (European Commission et al., 2013). As such, there is an ongoing need to improve how climate aspects are addressed in EIAs to ensure that the climate dimension is integrated into the environmental assessment. Stronger provisions either in the EIA Directive or in the transposition of the Directives into national law could help guide actors in better recognising embodied carbon in the approval process, making these emissions a more influential aspect in decision-making and increasing transparency.

Box 4.1. Best practice: Guidelines on climate considerations in Swedish EIAs

In Sweden, the STA (2022b) and the Swedish Protection Agency (2024) recognise that EIAs are inherently complex because emissions often have global rather than localised impacts. This results in a global sphere of influence, with many consequences arising from cumulative effects. Specifically, in the case of road and rail projects, environmental assessments account for the climate impact during both construction and operation phases. During construction, emissions are generated from machinery, transportation of materials, and the production of key materials such as concrete and metals, which are significant sources of greenhouse gases.

As a result, the STA (2022a) drafted a set of guidelines allowing for improved climate impact assessment by subcontractors conducting the EIAs. Specifically, through these guidelines, the STA exceeds the requirements on climate impact assessment for EIA approval as set out by responsible authorities.

²¹ Reglugerð um umhverfismat framkvæmda og áætlana (1381/2021).

5. Embodied carbon in nordic public procurement practices

Public procurement can be regarded as a vital instrument for promoting low-carbon transport infrastructure construction. As such, Section 5.1 outlines the relevance of GPP to achieving carbon reduction goals, while Section 5.2 explores key opportunities and effective practices in the Nordic countries. A summary of the main findings is provided in Table 5-1, followed by a detailed discussion in the subsequent paragraphs.

5.1 Public procurement: A powerful tool for delivering low-carbon transport infrastructure

Figure 5-1. Public procurement spending as percentage of GDP

Source: Ramboll based on figures from the OECD (2021)

Public procurement is considered an essential tool to steer towards low-carbon transport infrastructure construction.

15 % of global emissions can be attributed to public procurement, of which construction products are responsible for 12 % (Mission Possible Partnership & World Economic

Forum, 2022). Data on GHG emissions from road and rail infrastructure construction is scarce, also in the Nordics. In Sweden, climate impact of all public purchases amounted to 23.5 million tonnes of CO₂e in 2019, with rail and road infrastructure construction accounting for 1.3 million tonnes of CO₂e in 2022, roughly 6 % of all public procurement (Upphandlingsmyndigheten, 2021; WSP & Trafikverket, 2023).

When public procurement practices contain environmental or sustainability considerations, it is also referred to as green public procurement (GPP). As per the European Commission (2008), green public procurement is a procedure through which public authorities look to acquire products, services, and projects that have a lower environmental impact throughout their lifecycle compared to similar products, services and projects. Specifically for transport infrastructure construction, this means that GPP can contribute to reductions in embodied carbon and unlock sustainable construction (ECOS, 2024).

By incorporating GPP criteria in their procurement practices, public entities can set the example towards low-carbon transport infrastructure construction, showcasing how embodied carbon can be considered when rewarding public contracts. Not only does GPP contribute to the implementation of national strategies through a practical tool which can be applied specifically to transport infrastructure construction, but GPP also stimulates market innovation by encouraging contractors to develop the sustainability of their services directly (European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, 2016). Therefore, GPP should be recognised as a powerful tool to guide the construction sector towards a low-carbon future (Cox & Bergmeister, 2024).

As GPP requirements and award criteria can easily be adjusted, there is room for a great deal of flexibility and adaptability.

Firstly, public procurers can customise GPP criteria on sector, project-, or material-level. Requirements and award criteria can go beyond national strategies to explore how the most immediate impact can be made in the transition to low-carbon transport infrastructure construction. Secondly, public procurers have the possibility to include GPP criteria in their procurement practices as requirements contractors have to adhere to, or as award criteria on which contractors can compete without a minimum level to be reached, or both. This allows a great degree of freedom to public procurers on how they would like to consider embodied carbon and other environmental considerations (European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment, 2016).

The potential of GPP to accelerate the green transition is recognized on a European level. To support GPP in the EU Member States, the European Commission provides GPP criteria for various sectors. These criteria are voluntary

recommendations designed to allow procurers to integrate environmental considerations into their procurement practices. Even though some mandatory GPP requirements are set for buildings on energy efficiency through the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, mandatory requirements for transport infrastructure construction are to be set on national level (Sapir et al., 2022).

Despite this, the uptake of GPP in transport infrastructure construction remains rather limited on European level, due to difficulties surrounding criteria definitions, lacking administrative capacity among procuring agencies, legal uncertainties and associated risks (Cox & Bergmeister, 2024).

The complexity surrounding GPP increases due to the variety of procurement models which can be used, hindering further alignment on GPP integration in procurement practices.

This is also the case in the Nordics, where several procurement models are used, such as Design-Bid-Build, Design-Build and integrated project delivery models (e.g., Project Alliance models in Finland).

5.2 Embodied carbon considerations through GPP in construction

Table 5-1. GPP in public construction across the Nordic countries

		Iceland	Norway	Finland	Sweden	Denmark
General GPP practices	National GPP strategy	Non-mandatory guidelines called 'Græn skref' (Green steps) to support GPP.	Since 2024, it has been mandatory for climate and environment needs to be weighted at least 30% in every public procurement as per national law.	The Finnish National Procurement Act (1397/2016) encourages and enables the consideration of environmental and social aspects in public procurement.	The National Public Procurement Strategy (2017) includes goals on public procurement that drive innovation and promote alternative solutions and public procurement that is environmentally responsible.	A strategy for GPP (2020) is part of the strategy goal of cutting carbon emissions by 70% in Denmark by 2030.

Table 5-1. GPP in public construction across the Nordic countries (continued)

		Iceland	Norway	Finland	Sweden	Denmark
General GPP practices	GPP internal policy in infrastructure bodies	The Icelandic Road Administration follows the national strategy.	Infrastructure bodies follow the requirements set out at national level. The road infrastructure body experiments with a bonus-malus scheme on climate impact.	The FTIA employs environmental criteria in many of its procurements.	Procurement practices align with requirements set for government agencies, encompassing not only environmental considerations but also social dimensions.	Neither rail nor road infrastructure bodies have developed a GPP strategy, but they have attempted to harmonise carbon measurement.
	GWP considerations	Focus on embodied carbon through award criteria in GPP	GWP has not been used in project award criteria. GPP practices are to be developed with the implementation of an LCA tool.	Focus beyond embodied carbon, with tests on bonus-malus scheme. Carbon budgeting through requirement or award criteria.	GWP has not been used in project award criteria and will not be in the near future. Instead, sustainability agreements are made. See Box 5.3 for more details.	GWP is not included as award criteria in public procurement projects but is included as threshold values that contractors have a duty to meet.
		Required GWP documentation	No documentation requirements on GWP data.	Generally, environmental data is to be provided in the form of EPDs, for both rail and road.	No documentation requirements for GWP data for procurement.	Data beyond the Climate Calculation tool ('Klimatkalkyl') must be verified through documentation (such as an EPD or equivalent certificate verifying material requirements).

Infrastructure bodies' approach to embodied carbon reduction

Most Nordic infrastructure bodies incorporate GPP into their procurement policy, thereby following up or exceeding national strategies on GPP, which are voluntary. By doing so, infrastructure bodies bridge the gap resulting from national government guidelines, which often lack a specific focus on decarbonisation of transport infrastructure construction.

Additionally, no mandatory rules on GPP implementation in procurement are imposed in the Nordic countries.

However, mandatory climate and environmental considerations were recently introduced in Norway. As described in the box below, Norway has taken a promising step towards minimising the environmental impact of public procurement by making GPP mandatory to include in procurement practices. This requirement is, however, not specific to construction and its practical implementation remains uncertain.

Box 5.1. Good practice: Mandatory climate and environment considerations in Norwegian Public Procurement

At the beginning of 2024, Norway introduced a new law requiring that climate and environmental considerations must account for at least 30% of the evaluation criteria in all public procurement processes (DFØ, n.d.). Exceptions can be made only if it is proven through written justification that these criteria are not suitable for the specific project.

This regulation is expected to significantly influence infrastructure projects, affecting both the awarding of contracts and their execution. Public purchasers can apply for an exemption if they can demonstrate that imposing minimum requirements for climate and environmental considerations will yield a greater positive impact than the 30% weighting.

While the law has broad support as a positive step towards reducing the environmental impact of public procurement, there is still uncertainty about its practical application. A common concern is that mandating a 30% weighting for climate and environmental criteria in every tender might limit the ability to adequately consider other important factors, such as quality or competence. This could, in some cases, fail to achieve an overall reduction in environmental impact. Developing transparent and robust guidelines for conducting carbon assessments in infrastructure projects is thus essential to achieving real emissions reductions.

Nevertheless, in most Nordic countries, infrastructure bodies take the lead in introducing GPP requirements. This includes the FTIA in Finland and the STA in Sweden, both of which are responsible for road as well as rail infrastructure asset management and construction. In Sweden, most infrastructure projects are mandated to reduce their climate impact, as explained in more depth in Box 5.2. In the case of the FTIA in Finland, procurement policy is developed with the aim of reducing embodied carbon through incorporating environmental criteria into procurements. This is done specifically through a focus on emissions calculations, life cycle costs and circularity. For more examples of the procurement policy of FTIA, see Box 5.3. In Norway, the road infrastructure bodies adopted a different approach by incentivising low-carbon solutions in tenders, while allowing contractors the

flexibility to select climate mitigation measures most suitable for the project at hand. While this is considered efficient on paper, to what extent this leads to a real-time reduction in climate impact is also disputed.

Still, not all infrastructure bodies have developed their own strategy, as some align themselves more with the national strategy on GPP (e.g. IRCA in Iceland and the Danish road and rail infrastructure bodies). Considering that, as mentioned, the national strategies are often lacking in specific ambitions, infrastructure bodies consequently also fail to harness the potential of GPP to stimulate embodied carbon reduction in transport infrastructure construction. As a result, these infrastructure bodies lack clear climate targets and low-carbon requirements in their procurement policy.

Box 5.2. Good practice: How the Swedish Transport Administration (STA) implements climate requirements in procurement

STA climate requirements in procurement

The Swedish Transport Administration (STA) requires contractors to reduce the climate impact of infrastructure projects in line with the STA's climate targets. These requirements, in place since 2016, address emissions from materials, construction activities, and future maintenance.

- For development projects over SEK 50 million, the STA sets a project-specific baseline carbon budget using the climate calculation tool (Klimatkalkyl), based on 2015 emissions data. Next, requirements to reduce emissions in line with the STA's reduction targets are included in the procurement specification. Upon project completion, the contractor submits a climate declaration to verify that agreed reductions are achieved and may receive bonuses for surpassing targets or incur fines for failing to meet them (Swedish Transport Administration, 2023).
- For all projects, materials-specific requirements are set for key product groups (steel, concrete and cement, asphalt, vehicles, working equipment and fuels), with values determined by the project's completion year. Materials must be verified using GWP data (from product EPDs or the use of EPDs of equivalent products, covering life cycle modules A1-A3) and approved by the STA. Similar to large projects, bonuses or fines may also be applied based on performance (Swedish Transport Administration, 2023).

A 2023 evaluation of the climate requirements from the STA concludes that, while the requirements do support climate mitigation efforts and capacity building within the industry, it remains unclear whether the STA is on track to meet its climate targets. Climate requirements are applied to most projects; however, not all projects have met their specific reduction targets. The report indicates that most reduction targets were set at 10–20% compared to the baseline (Blomqvist et al., 2023).

Embodied carbon reduction through GPP requirements

Across the Nordics, the common narrative is that considerations of GWP are first and foremost addressed as requirements that contractors must adhere to, rather than through award criteria. While set requirements ensure a minimum reduction in embodied carbon, they do not necessarily encourage competing contractors to reduce embodied carbon to the largest extent possible, as would be the case if embodied carbon were also included as award criteria.

In Sweden, GWP is currently also not included as award criteria in public procurement projects, but rather as requirements to which all contractors must adhere. GPP requirements are in place for specific materials (e.g. concrete/cement, reinforced steel, asphalt) and for vehicles and machinery used on the construction site. However, alongside these requirements, the STA does hand out fines and bonuses to contractors after project completion, based on whether greater or fewer GHG emissions are emitted compared to

what was shared in the design plan. While this mechanism is not an award criterion for GWP, it does act as a tool to hold contractors accountable for their GHG emissions. For more specific information on this approach by the STA, see Box 5.2.

The FTIA in Finland takes another approach, by employing mainly environmental criteria in many of its procurements, rather than setting targets related to embodied carbon.

These environmental criteria include minimum requirements, comparative criteria, or bonuses related to the management or implementation of environmental matters. In investment projects, environmental criteria are currently in use for the emission classes of trucks and construction machinery, among others. In Box 5.3, the FTIA's approach towards sustainable procurement practices is further highlighted. In Denmark, no mechanisms related to embodied carbon as award criteria are yet in place. However, limits on emissions for both concrete and steel are set in place by the Danish Road Directorate. Additionally, the Danish Road Directorate has initiated pilot projects with a focus on award criteria rather than limits-only, with the intention of stimulating competition on CO₂ reduction.

However, additional performance can also be recognised through award criteria, as is the case in Norway.

Here, additional climate performance in road infrastructure construction is weighed as an award criterion, meaning that if a contractor offers higher or lower emission reductions than is mandated, this will be taken into consideration through a bonus-malus scheme. The Norwegian Road agencies (NPRA, Nye Veier) are testing such a scheme specifically for the most carbon-intensive materials, but the extent to which

this bonus-malus scheme has stimulated emissions reduction is yet to be seen. The Norwegian rail infrastructure body also requires contractors competing in a tender to showcase the degree to which they can reduce their emissions compared to a carbon budget set by the road infrastructure bodies. This type of carbon budget exercise is set up both at a project and a materials level. In the latter, the 10–12 most carbon-intensive materials are to be included.

Box 5.3. Good practice: The Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency's roadmap towards sustainable procurement

The Finnish Transport Infrastructure Agency (FTIA) has been promoting low-carbon infrastructure construction by, among other things, updating procurement policy and enhancing procurement guidelines through a Green Deal on sustainable procurements. The focus of the FTIA has been on supporting the implementation of emissions calculations and producing information for the operational model of low-carbon procurements.

Specifically for paving contracts, the FTIA has long developed low-emissions procurement and has, together with the asphalt industry, recognised the need to find ways to reduce emissions from road paving activities. One identified method is the use of EPDs for asphalt and a common tool for their production. A roadmap for the implementation of requirements, created in 2018 and reviewed annually, outlines the measures and schedule to promote the adoption of EPDs in paving contracts. By 2026, the target is to include EPD-based calculations as part of guidance or as a bonus in several contracts, and to begin experimenting with emissions costs as part of the comparative price in contracts. For 2028, the target is for EPD-based calculations to be requested or utilised in most paving contracts. As a result, emissions would fundamentally guide the FTIA's procurement decisions for paving contracts (FTIA, 2023).

Alongside this, the FTIA also has an agreement on emissions-free worksites. The objective of the agreement is to reduce emissions generated in the worksites through public procurement on a long-term basis. By the end of 2025, participating worksites are expected to transition to fossil-free fuels. Furthermore, the agreement sets a target for 50% of the machinery and transport operations at these worksites to be fuelled by electricity, biogas, or hydrogen by the end of 2030 (Finnish Ministry of the Environment, 2024).

Documentation requirements on embodied carbon

To assess and verify the embodied carbon of infrastructure construction projects, data collection through documentation is key (as also highlighted in Section 4.2). However, across the Nordic countries, requirements relating to the documentation of data on embodied carbon are limited. Some countries, such as Iceland and Finland, do not require any documentation on GWP to be submitted to the procuring authority at all. In Sweden, documentation is to be submitted only if this is not an emissions factor accounted for in the climate calculation tool to verify the data purposes.

When GWP documentation is required to be submitted, this is usually through an EPD (Sweden, Denmark, Norway).

Through the submission of GWP documentation, data on embodied carbon can be assured and verified.

In Norway, EPDs are to be submitted to verify environmental data for the bonus-malus scheme for road infrastructure construction. For rail infrastructure, EPDs are required for the most carbon-intensive materials when contractor parties are being selected, at the tender stage. Consequently, through this requirement, suppliers are encouraged to routinely produce project-specific EPDs for larger infrastructure projects.

In Denmark, rail and road infrastructure bodies both request EPDs as part of their contract documents. In the case of road infrastructure, an EPD is generally requested for projects over DKK 5 million (Excl. VAT). When no EPD is provided, or when the upper-limit criteria on carbon emissions are reached, the contractor might be fined. For rail infrastructure, LCA is also to be shared.

Benchmark values for embodied carbon in GPP

Of all the Nordic countries, only Sweden has a baseline for CO₂ emissions for larger projects, based on historical data and modelling. In practice, target levels depend on project type, taking account specific components of e.g. roads, bridges and tunnels. As highlighted in Box 3.1 and Chapter 2, the STA adopted reduction targets based on an impact assessment, which revealed that the goals are achievable without significant cost increases (Uppenberg et al., 2015).

While the Danish road infrastructure body does have the ambition of setting such benchmark values, they lack the database required to set specific limits. In the case of Norway, no benchmark value for CO₂ is provided. However, there are climate budgets set to award criteria, through which contractors are weighted on, among other things, their proposed reduction compared to the benchmark budget.

All in all, while GPP integration in Nordic infrastructure projects has increased, its full potential has not yet been recognised. This is the case despite procurement being one of the main instruments for public entities to influence practices and create demand for low-carbon materials and solutions, as pointed out in Section 5.1. While some countries have established practices for requiring emissions data, others are still developing the necessary methodologies and tools.

As such, to overcome challenges related to implementing GPP requirements at project level (e.g. benchmarking, measuring and monitoring carbon performance throughout the projects), it may be beneficial to further set materials-specific requirements through EPDs. This approach allows for more precise accountability of carbon impacts at materials level, supporting more effective carbon management of carbon-intensive materials throughout the project's life cycle.

6. Takeaways and suggested actions

This section outlines the key takeaways from the study and presents actionable recommendations for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure. Section 6.1 summarises the findings of the study, providing an overview of the current situation and challenges in managing embodied carbon across the Nordic countries. Section 6.2 identifies key action areas and offers targeted recommendations for implementing effective measures, focusing on practical strategies to enhance embodied carbon reduction in infrastructure construction.

6.1 Summary of findings

Historically, transport infrastructure policy has focused on emissions from transportation and vehicle use, while impacts from constructing, maintaining and redeveloping the infrastructure have received less attention. This review indicates a shift in priorities, with embodied carbon gaining increased focus in the Nordic transport infrastructure sector.

Overall, the report shows that important advancements have already been implemented across the Nordic countries, but significant opportunities exist for developing more comprehensive approaches to managing and reducing the embodied carbon in transport infrastructure. Numerous initiatives are present across the region to support the adoption of low-carbon solutions in infrastructure design and construction. This indicates a frontrunner position that serve as inspiration for other European countries and beyond. Embodied carbon considerations have become a more prominent part of the policy agenda, underscoring the Nordic region's commitment to better addressing these emissions sources. Comprehensive tools and guidelines for assessing and managing embodied carbon performance are in place, but their integration into strategic frameworks and procurement processes, including the sourcing of low-carbon alternatives for materials where appropriate, remains underdeveloped. As such, embodied carbon performance receives less consideration in decision-making.

Integrating emissions reduction goals throughout project planning, design and execution across all activities, stakeholders, and members of the value chain is complex. As a result, even if there are several approaches to lowering embodied carbon in transport infrastructure – such as choosing low-carbon materials, optimising designs to reduce materials use, and increasing recycling and reuse – current efforts frequently fall short of achieving substantial emissions reductions.

Rail and road infrastructure authorities typically serve as primary actors responsible for managing embodied carbon within infrastructure projects, often in collaboration with external contractors. Through this partnership, consistent and measurable reductions in embodied carbon can be made at project level. Infrastructure planning, EIA and public procurement involve a wider array of stakeholders.

Decision-making structures are generally consistent across Nordic countries, with only minor differences in the specific roles and responsibilities of actors involved. Figure 6-1 presents an overview of the responsibilities of different actors in construction projects management processes relevant for embodied carbon: 1) planning process, 2) carbon management, 3) EIAs, and 4) public procurement. The figure shows that the Nordic countries share broadly similar decision-making structures, but they differ slightly when it comes and the allocation of responsibilities to specific actors. Differences among the Nordic countries are found in GPP and final project approval, with responsibility for GPP policy divided between ministries and infrastructure bodies and variations in the government's role in project approval processes.

Figure 6-1. Overview of main aspects and actors involved in addressing embodied carbon in Nordic infrastructure

		Denmark				Finland				Iceland				Norway				Sweden			
		Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors	Ministry	Supervising entities	Infrastructure bodies	External actors
Planning	Identification of need																				
	Feasibility studies																				
	Final project approval	*								*											
	Design																				
	Construction																				
Carbon management	Targets on embodied carbon in infrastructure																				
	Monitoring embodied carbon performance																				
	Ownership of carbon assessment tool																				
	Conducting carbon assessment																				
	Carbon shadow pricing																				
EIA	Commissioning EIA																				
	Conducting EIA																				
	Approving EIA																				
Public procurement	Providing policy on GPP																				
	Requiring GWP documentation																				
	Verifying of EPDs																				
	Benchmarks values																				

Legend

- Main actor involved
- Supporting actor
- No current implementation

*Final approval provided by parliament

Note: This is a simplified overview; variations will occur depending on project size and type as well as procurement model. The role of procurement authorities is not highlighted in this overview.

6.2 A general framework for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure

Based on the study findings, it is possible to identify a set of key action areas by which embodied carbon can be addressed throughout the infrastructure project planning process (see Table 6-1). These action areas are: (i) embodied carbon targets and framework; (ii) carbon assessment, tools and data management; (iii) environmental impact assessment and (iv) public procurement. The table also reflects important action points for supporting embodied carbon reductions in transport infrastructure and can be used as a practical tool to assess ambition levels and guide future efforts across the Nordic region and beyond. Catering to different levels of ambition is key, as each country has a distinct context and associated governance structure that influences transport

infrastructure construction. Thus, while the highlighted key action areas offer insights on themes to consider when addressing embodied carbon, they should be taken up in reference to each country's specific context.

Ultimately, there is no silver bullet for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure. Instead, a combination of actions is required to effectively manage and reduce these emissions in the Nordic countries and beyond. The action areas presented below provide a robust foundation for reducing transport infrastructures' climate impact, while acknowledging different maturity and ambition levels.

Table 6-1. Key action areas for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure

		Level 0 (low ambition)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (highest ambition)
Embodied carbon targets, databases and framework	Specific embodied carbon targets on transport infrastructure	Embodied carbon is not acknowledged as part of the strategy.	Embodied carbon is acknowledged as part of the strategy, but no specific targets are set.	Partial targets for embodied carbon (i.e. for certain life cycle modules), initial focus on reducing GWP for high-carbon materials.	Complete targets for embodied carbon, includes specific, long-term GWP limits for carbon-intensive materials.
	Framework on embodied carbon assessment	No framework to support embodied carbon assessments.	Embodied carbon assessments are voluntary.	Embodied carbon assessments are conditionally mandatory (e.g. based on project size or type).	Embodied carbon assessments are always mandatory.
	Embodied carbon performance monitoring	No monitoring of embodied carbon.	Basic monitoring with no connection to targets.	Monitoring with defined targets, but not necessarily used for decision-making.	Comprehensive monitoring against targets with effective management reporting, supporting data-driven decision-making.
	Database (monitoring carbon performance)	No database.	Carbon assessment is documented with one value only, but detailed carbon assessment is not collected and stored.	Detailed carbon assessment is collected and stored, but the database is closed.	Open national database for detailed carbon assessments, with product-level data to enable benchmarking of materials by quantities, GWP values and costs.
Carbon assessment, tools and data management	Embodied carbon assessment methods	No specified standards or guidelines which should be used.	Basic guidelines established.	Standards and common assessment methods are followed through a specific tool.	Standards and assessment methods are aligned and can be implemented independently of any specific tool.

Table 6-1. Key action areas for addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure (continued)

		Level 0 (low ambition)	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3 (highest ambition)
Carbon assessment, tools and data management	Tools for carbon assessments	No specific tools.	Basic tools in use, e.g. Excel.	Advanced tools standardised across projects.	Sophisticated and dynamic BIM-connected tools.
	Database (emission factors)	Global/generic database, minimal product-level specificity.	National, tool-based database including some product-level details.	Extensive, open-access national database with substantial product-specific data.	Verified national database for accounting with product-specific data and possibility for integration across tools (e.g. API interfaces).
EIA	Embodied carbon considerations in EIAs	No embodied carbon consideration in EIAs.	Embodied carbon assessment conducted as part of EIA on a voluntary basis.	Embodied carbon assessment required as part of in EIAs.	Embodied carbon impact is a determinative factor in EIA approval.
GPP	Embodied carbon considerations in procurement policy	Embodied carbon is not considered in procurement.	Embodied carbon is considered voluntarily in procurement, with initial incentives to encourage low-carbon solutions.	Embodied carbon considerations are conditionally mandatory (e.g. based on project size or type), with ambitious requirements.	Embodied carbon considerations are always mandatory, with robust, specific carbon targets integrated across all policies.
	Result in embodied carbon reduction through procurement	Embodied carbon reduction through procurement does not occur.	Procurement practices that contribute to embodied carbon reductions are applied, but on an inconsistent basis.	Procurement that contributes to embodied carbon reduction is consistently applied, with specific thresholds on carbon-intensive materials.	Systematic procurement practices that strongly enhance embodied carbon reduction and applied in all projects.

6.3 Recommendations for continued efforts and improvements on addressing embodied carbon in transport infrastructure in the Nordic countries

To drive progress and advances in key action areas, continued knowledge-sharing and strengthening of capacity-building initiatives within and across the Nordic countries should be continued. These efforts allow for the enhancement of carbon assessments and public procurement practices, greater ambition among stakeholders, but also a better match between what the infrastructure bodies demand and what the market can provide. In practice, collaborative knowledge platforms, such as the successful Nordic coordination forums, can spur sector-wide capacity building and alignment on these topics. Below, targeted recommendations for further addressing embodied carbon are presented for each action area. Although these recommendations reflect key action points across the Nordic region, some of these recommendations may already have been implemented in one or more of the Nordic countries. Consequently, the recommendations should be interpreted in reference to a country's specific context.

To improve management of embodied carbon in transport infrastructure, various sector actors can take action. Accordingly, each recommendation will be accompanied by an indication of the (likely) affiliated actor(s), namely:

Ministries

Infrastructure bodies

Supervising entities

External actors

This classification allows for the delivery of actions in a targeted and effective way, facilitating improved implementation. The following recommendations outline key actions to advance embodied carbon management within transport infrastructure:

Recommendations for establishing embodied carbon targets, databases and frameworks

Establish specific embodied carbon targets.

As general objectives tend not to be effective in driving low-carbon performance at sectoral level, it is recommended that further sectoral embodied carbon targets are specified following overarching national goals. In the Nordic region, infrastructure bodies are typically responsible for establishing these sectoral targets (within infrastructure management). If sectoral bodies fail to provide such targets at their own initiative, authorities at political and ministerial level could mandate the infrastructure sector – equally to the building sector – to develop strategies and specific embodied carbon targets (e.g. carbon-intensive materials) to align with national climate goals.

Establish a consistent performance framework for embodied carbon assessment.

Through a systematic, mandatory framework, embodied carbon assessment can be integrated into the main transport infrastructure management process to allow for comprehensive monitoring. Important aspects to cover are the strategic application of carbon data in all project phases, the use of shadow carbon pricing that reflects true costs, and the integration of embodied carbon considerations into early decision-making.

Develop open-access databases for monitoring and benchmarking projects and portfolio-level carbon performance.

This improves the understanding of transport infrastructure emissions, supports transparency and increase accountability in national goal-tracking. As of now, the Nordic countries have made significant strides in developing reliable and open-access emissions databases (material/product and activities), but fewer efforts have focused on processes and databases for collecting, monitoring and reporting project and portfolio-level carbon performance. Open-access databases with this information will improve the understanding of transport infrastructure emissions, support transparency, and increase accountability in national goal-tracking.

Recommendations for carbon assessment, tools and data management

Develop consistent carbon assessment methodology to ensure comparability between projects and tools.

Key areas for alignment include identifying which projects and project phases should undergo carbon assessments, determining which life cycle modules to include, addressing land-use change impacts, and defining approaches for calculating materials and activity-based emissions factors for future projects. This can be facilitated through the provision of sophisticated and dynamic BIM-connected carbon assessment tools. Achieving consistent carbon assessment should be pursued through collaboration and industry input, aiming to set ambitious yet realistic expectations within national contexts.

Initialise benchmarking of embodied carbon reduction at product level.

Through benchmarking, generic GWP data with low product-level specificity can be replaced by product-specific alternatives. For example, benchmarking can be conducted along product material categories (cement, concrete, steel, iron) and further divided into performance sub-groups (e.g. cement grades C20, C30, C40) to track data on quantities, GWP values and costs to monitor the development of the green premium.

Recommendations for addressing embodied carbon through EIAs

Integrate the assessment of embodied carbon into EIAs.

This can be achieved by establishing embodied carbon as a determinative criterion for granting project approval, ensuring that the full life cycle emissions of proposed developments are systematically evaluated and considered.

Increase transparency of carbon sources from the planning phase onwards.

This can be achieved by incorporating detailed emissions forecasts by source into EIAs, in alignment with relevant standards (e.g. EN-15643-5 for sustainability assessments of civil engineering projects).

Recommendations for addressing embodied carbon through GPP

Develop detailed sector-specific guidelines for GPP.

To enable consistent and effective embodied carbon considerations through GPP, tailored guidelines for the sector are required. These should outline clear criteria for carbon-intensive materials, encourage the use of low-carbon alternatives while emphasising material efficiency and circularity, with a strong focus on the life cycle perspective. This will allow market evolution towards low-carbon materials and solutions to be driven further, allowing for specific embodied carbon reduction targets across projects. However, to achieve meaningful impact, requirements and incentives must be systematically aligned with the specific sector, project type and procurement model.

Encourage the use of Life Cycle Costing (LCC).

GPP processes can further address embodied carbon by incorporating LCC assessments to evaluate construction bids. LCC enables consideration of economic, social and environmental sustainability alongside financial factors. By accounting for long-term costs and benefits, LCC supports the selection of tenders that deliver sustainable outcomes, including improved resource efficiency, reduced environmental impacts, and long-term economic value.

Require contractors to submit EPDs for carbon-intensive materials in public procurement processes.

GPP processes can further address embodied carbon by incorporating LCC assessments to evaluate construction bids. LCC enables consideration of economic, social and environmental sustainability alongside financial factors. By accounting for long-term costs and benefits, LCC supports the selection of tenders that deliver sustainable outcomes, including improved resource efficiency, reduced environmental impacts, and long-term economic value.

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